

AWARENESS ON GLOBAL WARMING OF RURAL AND URBAN AREA B.Ed. STUDENTS WITH REGARD TO FREQUENT INTERNET USAGE

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ABSTRACT

This paper examined the awareness on global warming of rural and urban area B.Ed. students with regard to frequent internet usage. The sample for present study consisted of 150 B.Ed. students from rural area and 150 B.Ed. students from urban area of Tirunelveli District. The investigator used the survey method of research to study the awareness on global warming of rural and urban area B.Ed. students with respect to frequent internet usage. The investigator used the self-made tool and named as "Awareness on Global Warming Scale". From the results of t-test, there is no significant difference in awareness on global warming of rural and urban B.Ed. students with respect to daily internet usage.

KEYWORDS : Awareness, Global warming, B.Ed. students, Internet usage

INTRODUCTION

Over the past century, the world has warmed, ranging from 0.3 to 0.6 °C. It does not sound like much of a change until one realizes that over the past 10,000 years, the average global temperature has never been more than about 1°C warmer or cooler than it is to play. This warming is attributed to the increased industrial and other human activities. Climatologists have warned that if these activities are unchecked, they will cause rise in global temperature from 1.5 to 4°C over the next half century and endanger the existence of living things on the Earth. Of all the planets in our solar system, the Earth is remarkably unique in possessing so comfortable and hospitable average temperature of 15°C- a level of comfort unmatched any where in our solar system. On the other hand, our neighboring planets Venus, Jupiter, Mercury are too hot while Mars, Saturn, Uranus, Neptune and Pluto are freezing cold. The Earth has had this stable climate for the past 12,000 to 14,000 years. The temperature and its accompanying climate have been eminently suitable for growth of all living things. Thus in solar system, the Earth alone is habitable owing its uniqueness to the beneficent atmosphere. The most important aspect of balancing between the solar radiation absorbed and radiation reflected from the Earth's surface and atmosphere is that the green house gases keep the earth comfortably. Cool by sending out into the space part of the heat they absorb. It by any reason the heat that is going out into the space is blocked, i.e. the infrared windows are closed, excess of heat is stored in the atmosphere and the earth would get warmer. If the concentration of the green house gases increases, number of molecules that absorb infrared radiations will also increase. These extra molecules absorb the heat, which otherwise would have escaped into the space, and cause global warming, of the few results on the green house effect that seem straight forward and undisputedly accepted by green house scientists are (1) the world has warmed ranging from 0.3 to 0.6 over the past century and (2) the levels of naturally occurring atmospheric trace gases such as carbon dioxide, methane, nitrous oxide and ozone (in troposphere) have risen sharply over pre-industrial levels while chlorofluorocarbons and other halocarbons released by the industrial society have become a new class of radioactively important trace gases.

SIGNIFICANCE OF THE STUDY

In recent years global warming has become a big challenge to the world community and scientific society. It is a universal problem being associated with an abnormal increase in the level of temperature of the earth and its atmosphere. The global average temperature near Earth's surface has risen by 0.74 ± 0.18 C during the last 100 years. The Inter - governmental panel on climate change in its climatic models has projected that global surface temperatures is likely to increase by 1.1 to 6.4C between 1990-2100. The world's climatic system is fundamental to support life on this planet. Anthropogenic activities are altering the world's climate by

increasing the atmospheric concentration of green house gases, thereby amplifying the natural "green house effect" that makes the earth habitable, leading to detrimental and deleterious effects. Overall, climatic change is projected to increase threats to human health, predominantly within tropical and subtropical countries. Climatic change can affect the human health directly, through weather extremes and indirectly, through changes in the ranges of disease vectors, water borne pathogens, outbreak of epidemics, by bringing changes in water quality, air quality and food availability as well as food quality. Climatic changes triggered by global warming can bring in their wake extreme conditions like storms, drought and floods and can be of immediate threat to life. Global warming is a global warming. It is an environmental challenge. Rampant deforestation along with population growth, inappropriate technology, intensive agriculture, polluting industry and unplanned urbanization have led to the emission of green house gases like CO₂, NO₂, CH₄ and CFC which in turn raise the temperature of earth at an alarming rate contribute to global warming, there by endangering the whole universe. There is a crying need to prevent global warming because if the nature has power to give life, it has also power to cease life on earth. It is a right time to prevent the world from global warming. It can be done through the education. As we know, that "Today's child is the future citizen of tomorrow", as quoted by pundit Jawaharlal Nehru. So the students must be aware of the global warming. There is much more need of the study in the present generation which lacks awareness about the global warming. The shaping of attitude and values, commitment and skills needed to preserve and protect the environment begins at an early age during which the educators play an important role. School systems provide the largest organized sector for imparting education on the environment and initiating action. Teachers play a pivotal role towards such a reform. The promotion of awareness on global warming is essential, and citizens have a responsibility to take part in improving the environment's sustainability for the future. A sustainable environment means harmony between humans and nature while not jeopardizing the lives and opportunities of future generations. A focus on environmental sustainability has been increasingly present in our media. According to Butler and Pidgeon, media's role is "to deliver scientific information in ways necessary to allow citizens to make informed choices". Methods for delivering news have multiplied and evolved, originating with print, then adding radio, broadcast television, cable, and finally the Internet. With this background, the investigator made an attempt to make a study on the awareness on global warming.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

- To find out the level of awareness on global warming of rural and urban area B.Ed. students with respect to frequent internet usage.
- To find out whether there is any significant difference in

awareness on global warming of rural B.Ed. students with respect to frequent internet usage.

- To find out whether there is any significant difference in awareness on global warming of urban B.Ed. students with respect to frequent internet usage.

METHOD OF RESEARCH

The investigator used the survey method of research to study the awareness on global warming of rural and urban area B.Ed. students with respect to frequent internet usage.

POPULATION

The populations of the study consist of B.Ed. students of B.Ed. colleges from rural and urban area in Tirunelveli district.

SAMPLE

The sample for present study consists of 150 B.Ed. students from rural area and 150 B.Ed. students from urban area of Tirunelveli District.

TOOL USED

The investigator used the self-made tool and named as "Awareness on Global Warming Scale".

STATISTICAL TECHNIQUES USED

Mean, Standard Deviation and t-test

DESCRIPTIVE ANALYSIS OF DATA

To find out the Level of Awareness on global warming of rural and urban area B.Ed. students with respect to Internet usage.

Table - 1 Level of Awareness on global warming of rural and urban area B.Ed. students with respect to Internet usage

Location of the college	Yes						No					
	Low		Avg.		High		Low		Avg.		High	
	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%
Rural	36	70.6	7	13.7	8	15.7	57	57.6	23	23.2	19	19.2
Urban	32	46.4	22	31.9	15	21.7	57	70.4	14	17.3	10	12.3

With regard to using internet frequently, more than 70.6 % of rural B.Ed. students have low level of awareness on global warming. But 46.4 % of urban B.Ed. students have low level of awareness on global warming. With regard to not using internet frequently, more than 57.6% of rural B.Ed. students have low level of awareness on global warming. But 70.4% of urban B.Ed. students have low level of awareness on global warming.

INFERENCE ANALYSIS OF DATA

H0 :1 There is no significant difference in awareness on global warming of rural B.Ed. students with respect to daily internet usage.

Table - 2 t-test showing the significant difference in awareness on global warming of rural B.Ed. students with respect to daily internet usage

Variable	Internet usage	N	Mean	S D	Calculated 't' value	Tabulated 't' value	Remark
Awareness on global warming	Yes	51	51.6667	9.81563	1.350	1.96	NS
	No	99	53.9394	9.73822			

It is inferred from the above table that the calculated 't' value [Awareness on global warming (1.350)] is less than the table value (1.96) for dt (298) at 5% level of significance. Hence the null hypothesis accepted. It indicates that there is no significant difference in awareness on global warming of rural B.Ed. students with respect to daily internet usage.

H0 :2 There is no significant difference in awareness on global warming of urban B.Ed. students with respect to daily internet usage.

Table - 3 t-test showing the significant difference in awareness on global warming of urban B.Ed. students with respect to daily internet usage

Variable	Internet use	N	Mean	S D	Calculated 't' value	Tabulated 't' value	Remark
Awareness on global warming	Yes	69	59.3043	13.19793	1.684	1.96	NS
	No	81	55.6914	13.00446			

It is inferred from the above table that the calculated 't' value [Awareness on global warming (1.684)] is less than the table value (1.96) for dt (298) at 5% level of significance. Hence the null hypothesis accepted. It indicates that there is no significant difference in awareness on global warming of urban B.Ed. students with respect to daily internet usage.

FINDINGS AND CONCLUSION

From the results of descriptive analysis, the investigator found that, with regard to using internet frequently, more than 70.6 % of rural B.Ed. students and 70.4% of urban B.Ed. students have low level of awareness on global warming. It clearly shows that majority of the rural and urban B.Ed. students have low level of awareness on global warming with regard to internet usage.

From the results of inferential analysis, the investigator found that there is no significant difference in awareness on global warming of rural and urban B.Ed. students with respect to daily internet usage. It clearly shows that daily internet usage by B.Ed. students do not influence their awareness on global warming. The reason may be that the B.Ed. students may not use internet positively. But they share information on popular culture, such as music, movies and sports. As more people around the world gain access to all the tools of the digital age, the internet will play a greater role in everyday life. And so far, people in emerging and developing nations say that the increasing use of the internet has been a good influence in the realms of education, personal relationships and the economy. But despite all the benefits of these new technologies, on balance people are more likely to say that the internet is a negative rather than a positive influence on morality. So the B.Ed. students should use internet for sharing information on environmental issues.

REFERENCES

- Dutt, N. (2007). Environmental pollution and control. Hyderabad: Neelkamal publications pvt.ltd.
- Madhkar(2003). Impact of Globalisation on Education. New Delhi: Author Press pvt. ltd.
- <http://via.library.depaul.edu/cgi/viewcontent.cgi?article=1010&context=cmnt>
- <https://web.vanderbilt.edu/resources/social-media/social-media-handbook/what-is-social-media/>
- <http://download.nos.org/srsec317newE/317EL23.pdf>
- <http://www.yourarticlelibrary.com/essay/need-for-environmental-awareness/42509/>
- http://www.ema.co.tt/new/images/emacorner/social_media.pdf
- https://www.researchgate.net/publication/307968837_The_Role_of_Social_Media_on_Environmental_Awareness_of_Undergraduate_Students_in_University_of_Ulaimani_in_Iraq
- https://link.springer.com/chapter/10.1007/978-3-319-25153-0_9
- <http://cmsenvvis.nic.in/Social-Media-Publication-2014.pdf>